

Message from the Editor

Dear Readers, Contributors and RC25 Colleagues,

It is a great pleasure to introduce the June 2024 issue to you. It is our 23rd issue in the history of ISA RC25. You will find a thematic part, hand-picked and edited by Keiji Fujiyoshi, the President of ISA RC25 and Rika Yamashita, and a non-thematic part. Guest editors provide a brief overview of the selection of articles 1-3, so I will only note that the authors represent scholars who took part in the Melbourne Congress of Sociology and presented during the RC25 ISA sessions.

In this short introduction, I will focus on three articles in the non-thematic section. The section opens with an article by Marthinus Conradie and Olga Lasocka-Belc dedicated to critical diversity literacy and structure-facing virtue among South African students. The researchers provide strong and useful conclusions about belonging and inclusion, identity and becoming aware of the biases and the potential conflict between what one is learning at the university and the views cultivated in other settings. It is a compelling work, that may be useful to educators and also an example of a qualitative approach and the analysis of interview materials. Remaining within educational settings, the article is followed by a mixed-method study amongst students about their experiences of first-year studies to become a teacher, with a special focus on the discourse on wellbeing and mental health that they produced during interviews. The article is prepared by a team of Albanian educators from Durres University who identified, using statistical methods, the above-average knowledge on mental health and well-being of higher education students of pedagogical faculty, yet they also found that the students were unaware of factors about their own mental health and wellbeing. The researchers identified the areas for concern of higher education institutions and tutors within. Last but not least, there is an interesting multimodal critical discourse analysis carried out by researchers from Thailand (Guangwei Wu and Savitri Gadavani), to identify how the middle class is represented in a Chinese magazine. Authors find that a homogenous and male-oriented representation may support the ideology of consumer culture, which is responsible for the establishment and reproduction of social stratification through consumption in China. The article provides an interesting insight into analytical approaches when dealing with a material from journals.

Before we publish the list of reviewers for the year 2024, I offer my sincere thanks to the reviewers who accepted our calls for review. It is an ongoing struggle to find suitable and willing scholars, with relevant expertise and experience. Your work is valuable and of great importance. Thank you once again.

With warm greetings to all RC25 members and beyond.

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